

Performance assessment of thermal sensors integrated in a 3D-printed fingertip

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Abstract—This study aims to evaluate the performance of two commercial temperature sensors integrated into a 3D-printed fingertip for hand prostheses. The performance of the two selected sensors (NTC and IR) was tested using a novel experimental setup and a systematic protocol. The results demonstrated that the infrared sensor is the optimal sensor for prosthetic fingertip integration due to its low rise time and mean absolute error. The proposed standardized method provides an accurate and reliable approach for evaluating thermal sensor performance in a realistic environment.

Index Terms—Prosthesis thermal sensors, characterization protocol, instrumented prosthetic hands

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of thermal sensors in hand prostheses can provide useful information to protect the hand and the user from damages. The sensory information could be adopted both for controlling the hand behaviour and for feeding back somatic sensations to the amputee. It aims at increasing prosthesis acceptability and safety. In literature there are still few examples of thermal sensors integrated in prosthetic devices [1]. In these studies, the selection process is driven only by the technical features, without considering how the sensor performance may be affected by its final application or real-world conditions. It is evident that a crucial unresolved matter pertains to the employment of a systematic assessment to select thermal sensors, specifically within the context of realistic operational conditions, which encompasses the integration of these sensors into prosthetic hands.

The objective of this study is to conduct a comprehensive and systematic comparison of the performance of two commercial temperature sensors when integrated into a prosthetic fingertip. The performance of the sensors was evaluated when inserted into a 3D-printed fingertip, with and without a silicone

cover, considering the contact with different object temperatures.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

In this study two thermal sensors, the *Negative Temperature Coefficient thermistor (NTC)* and *Infrared (IR)*, were selected and tested. The *NTC* was chosen based on the datasheet, which indicated that it would provide the best performance as a contact temperature sensor. Whereas, the *IR* sensor was selected as it is a contactless thermal sensor, which is able to detect nociceptive hot/cold information in advance, thereby avoiding contact with potentially dangerous temperatures. The two sensors were tested integrated in a 3D-printed fingertip with and without a silicone cover, to simulate the presence of a cosmetic glove.

A. Testing set-up

The characterisation procedure was conducted with the aid of a custom testbed, which was adapted from the one described in [2]. The configuration adopted is illustrated in Fig.1 and consists of three principal components: 1) *Positioning system*, a 3-axis Cartesian positioning system that comprises three linear stages (*PI VT-80*), with a spatial resolution of $0.5\mu\text{m}$. 2) *Sample holder*, mounted on the vertical axis of the positioning system, includes a 3D-printed fingertip into which each sensor is integrated. The entire fingertip including the *NTC* sensor was covered by the silicone layer, whereas in correspondence of the *IR* a hole was added. 3) *Thermal reference*, an aluminium object ($10 \times 10 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$) mounted over a Peltier cell. The temperature of the object is maintained at a constant level through the use of a thermal controller (*TEC controller*).

B. Protocol

The performance of the sensors integrated in the 3D-printed fingertip was assessed in order to ascertain how they might be affected when subjected to a more realistic scenario. The sensor was placed in contact with the thermal reference at different temperatures in the range $[15, 75] \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a step

This work was partially supported by: i) the EU Commission under the project SOMA (H2020-FETOPEN-2019-899822): Ultrasound peripheral interface and in-vitro model of human somatosensory system and muscles for motor decoding and restoration of somatic sensations in amputees, ii) the Italian Institute for Labour Accidents (INAIL) Prosthetic Center with the BioARMnext project (CUP: E57G23000260005).

Fig. 1. Experimental set-up. The three main components of the testing platform are reported: 1. Positioning system, 2. Sample holder, 3. Thermal reference.

of 10 °C. The experiment was repeated 3 times for each temperature value with and without the silicone cover. Lastly, the sensor was compared based on the analysis of the following indicators: *i*) Mean Absolute Error (MAE) [°C], *ii*) Repeatability Error [°C] [3], *iii*) Rise Time [s] [4]. The sensor that most closely aligns with the characteristics of human physiology (*Rise time*, *i.e.* reaction time to thermal stimulus: 0.94 [s] [5], *MAE*, *i.e.* minimal thermal variation detectable by humans: 0.5 [°C] [6]) was finally selected. A detail of the criteria used for selecting the protocol is provided in [7].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The obtained results are shown in Fig. 2. The *MAE* value for both the sensors without silicone cover is 2 °C for all the tested temperatures. Conversely, the *MAE* showed an increasing trend with the temperature when the fingertip was covered with a silicone layer. A comparable trend was also evident in the rise time for both sensors. This trend was further accentuated when the sensors were covered with the silicone layer. The repeatability error for all sensors at all temperatures was found to be lower than 1 °C, with an increasing trend observed to be higher with the silicone cover in both sensors.

The low *MAE* and repeatability error without the silicone cover demonstrate their independence from the temperature. The growing trend with the temperature of the considered indicators is more pronounced when a silicone cover is used, due to its insulating properties. Moreover, the IR exhibited an instantaneous rise time in all the analysed configurations, comparable to the physiological reaction time (0.94 s). This aspect ensured a rapid response of the prosthesis in critical situations, such as contact with objects at extreme temperatures. The *MAE* of the IR (3.3 ± 5.1 °C and 4 ± 5.4 °C with and without silicone cover) was the closest to the human one (± 0.5 °C), allowing to accurately discriminate between painful (15 °C, 55 °C) and tolerable critical temperatures (35 °C). This is fundamental to guarantee the safety and comfort of the prosthesis user, as it enables an appropriate response to potentially harmful scenarios. In addition, the ability of the IR sensor to measure temperature without physical contact with the object reduces prosthesis damage risk and enhances durability.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed analysis represents a significant advancement over existing literature, since it ensures a more rigorous and

Fig. 2. MAE, rise time and repeatability error reported for the IR and NTC sensors, at all the tested temperatures, integrated in a fingertip without (*WO*) a silicone cover on the left and with (*W*) a silicone cover on the right.

systematic approach for the selection of temperature sensors. It allowed a rigorous comparison between the performance of the NTC and IR sensors once integrated into a fingertip, considering two configurations: with and without a silicone cover. It enabled the determination of the IR sensor as the optimal choice for prosthesis applications. The IR was not fully covered by the silicone, as it would have sensed the temperature of the cover rather than the object, significantly degrading its performance. The obtained results outline that the presence of a cosmetic glove can negatively impact the performance of the sensors embedded in a prosthesis. Future works will be devoted to compare the performance of the IR fully and partially covered by a silicone cover. Moreover, the performance of the selected sensor will be tested once integrated in a prosthetic hand during the execution of grasping tasks.

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